

Effects of Thermoplastic Polymers on the Cure Kinetics and Morphology of Epoxy Blend Systems

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ABSTRACT

The cure kinetics of a diaminodiphenylsulphone (DDS) cured tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM) epoxy and its blend with polyetherimide (PEI) of various compositions were studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The morphology observation by using scanning electron microscopy has demonstrated phase separation of the epoxy-PEI blends during cure, which induced uneven segregation of the epoxy and amine in different domains. These factors affecting the cure kinetics were discussed. An autocatalytic mechanism was observed for the epoxy-PEI blends; however, the reaction rates for the epoxy blends were found to be higher than the neat epoxy. The proposed kinetic model has been found to describe well the cure behavior of the epoxy-PEI blends up to the vitrification point.

INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting epoxies are generally brittle due to high crosslink densities. Toughening epoxy matrices using liquid reactive rubbers has been widely reported in the literature [1-3]. However, rubber modification on epoxies becomes ineffective as the crosslink density of the epoxy matrix increases due to the inability of rubber particles to undergo shear yielding or cavitation when surrounded by a highly crosslinked network. Furthermore, toughness improvements in most rubber-modified thermosetting systems usually result in a significant decrease in T_g of the cured thermosetting resins. The T_g depression of

the modified epoxy matrices becomes severe, especially when the reactive rubbers are used at levels high enough to noticeably enhance the fracture toughness. As a result, alternatives were needed and recent studies have demonstrated that polymeric thermoplastics, such as polyethersulfones (PES) [4,5], polyetherimides (PEI) [6-9], and polycarbonate [10-12], poly(phenylene oxide) [13] or a combination of rubbers and thermoplastics [14], etc., can enhance fracture toughness without sacrificing T_g , strength, stiffness, or other desirable properties of thermosetting resin systems. Alloying with polysulfone or polyethersulfone with reactive functional groups has also been the recent focus of toughness improvement for epoxy resins [15].

Thermoplastics addition to epoxy resins is thus expected to not only alter the morphology but also the cure kinetics. Phase separation takes place and a heterogeneous morphology develops if the thermoplastic polymer and the crosslinked epoxy are not miscible after cure. While the cure kinetics and reaction mechanisms of various neat epoxy resins have been extensively studied by use of various methods including IR spectroscopy [16,17] and more often by differential scanning calorimetry [18-21], effects of thermoplastics additives to epoxy resins on cure kinetics have, however, rarely been investigated. By use of a kinetic modeling approach, we will show how thermosetting epoxy blends with a thermoplastic polymer (polyetherimide) will behave during cure.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy resin is tetraglycidyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (TGDDM) (Ciba-Geigy MY 720). The base epoxy resin and its blends with the polyetherimide (PEI) (GE Ultem^R-1010) were cured with an aromatic amine hardener, diaminodiphenylsulphone (DDS) (Ciba-Geigy HT976). Epoxy/PEI blended resin mixtures with 10, 20, 30, 50 phr PEI, respectively, were prepared, where "phr" is the parts of PEI per hundred parts of the TGDDM epoxy resin. First, PEI was weighed and dissolved completely in the methylene chloride solvent and the resulting polymer solution was mixed with the epoxy resin at room temperature. The solvent in the mixture was vaporized in a circulation oven with an exhaust fan at room temperature, followed by residual solvent removal in a hot vacuum oven for 8 h at 120 °C. Subsequently, 35 phr DDS (= 0.67 stoichiometric equivalent of epoxy) was slowly added into the resin-PEI mixture with continuous stirring in an isothermal oil bath kept at 120 °C.

To investigate the morphology change as a function of reaction progress, a series of blend samples of various cure extents were prepared. The polymer-epoxy blend samples were prepared in the oven at 177, 187, and 197 °C, respectively, and withdrawn from the oven at several time

intervals and quenched immediately to room temperature to freeze the reaction. To determine the extent of epoxy reactions at the time of withdrawal from the oven, the residual isothermal heat for the samples was measured with DSC. The extent of reaction for the samples was calculated from $\alpha_{Is} = (\Delta H_{Io} - \Delta H_{IR})/\Delta H_T$, where α_{Is} is the extent of reaction; ΔH_{Io} is the total reaction heat at 177 °C. ΔH_{IR} is the residual heat; and $\Delta H_T = \Delta H_{Io} + \Delta H_R$.

A power-compensated type of differential scanning calorimeter (Perkin-Elmer DSC 7) was used for isothermal cure experiments and data analysis. Prior to DSC runs, the temperature and heats of reaction were calibrated with indium and zinc standards. Samples (5-8 mg) were placed in DSC aluminum pans. Isothermal cure reaction was conducted at three temperatures (177, 187, and 197 °C, respectively). The reaction was considered complete when the isothermal DSC thermogram leveled off to the baseline, which generally took 2 hr. The total area under the exotherm curve, based on the extrapolated baseline at the end of the reaction, was used to calculate the isothermal heat of cure, ΔH_I (J/g). After the isothermal cure reaction was completed in the DSC, the sample was cooled to 40 °C. To determine the residual heat of reaction, ΔH_R (J/g), the samples after isothermal cure were scanned at 10 °C/min from 40 °C to 300 °C. The sum of both the isothermal heat (ΔH_I) and residual heat (ΔH_R) of reactions was taken to represent the total heat of cure (ΔH_T). The isothermal conversion at time t was defined as $\alpha_I(t) = \Delta H_I(t)/\Delta H_T$.

Kinetic Analytical Procedures. A general equation for autocatalytic cure reactions of many amine-cured epoxy systems is as following: [22-26]

$$r = d\alpha/dt = (k_1 + k_2 \cdot \alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

where α is the conversion, k_1 and k_2 are the apparent rate constants, r is the rate of reaction, and m and n are the kinetic exponents of the reactions. The constant k_1 of Eq. (4) can be calculated if the initial reaction rate at $\alpha = 0$ can be estimated. Both kinetic constants, k_1 and k_2 are assumed to be of the Arrhenius form: $k_1 = A_1 \exp(-E_{a1}/RT)$ and $k_2 = A_2 \exp(-E_{a2}/RT)$, where A is the pre-exponential constant, E_a is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

To obtain a first guess of the reaction order n , Eq. (4) is modified to the following form:

$$\ln(d\alpha/dt) = \ln(k_1 + k_2 \cdot \alpha^m) + n \cdot \ln(1 - \alpha) \quad (5)$$

Except for the initial region, a plot of $\ln(d\alpha/dt)$ versus $\ln(1-\alpha)$ is expected to be linear with a slope n . Eq. (4) can be re-arranged:

$$\ln\left\{\frac{d\alpha/dt}{(1-\alpha)^n} - k_1\right\} = \ln(k_2) + m \cdot \ln(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

The first term of Eq. (6) can be computed using the previously estimated k_1 and n values. Linearity is expected if the left term of Eq. (6) is plotted vs. $\ln(\alpha)$, yielding a straight line whose slope and intercept allow the estimation of the reaction order, m , and the autocatalyzed kinetic constant, k_2 , respectively. By applying the described procedure, preliminary kinetic parameters can be obtained on the first trial. However, to obtain more precise values, an iterative procedure should be utilized. Eq. (4) can be rearranged to give the following form:

$$\ln(d\alpha/dt) - \ln(k_1 + k_2 \cdot \alpha^m) = n \cdot \ln(1 - \alpha) \quad (7)$$

Now with k_2 , m , and n estimated from the stated procedures, the left terms of Eq. (7) can be plotted vs. $\ln(1-\alpha)$. A new value of the reaction order n can be obtained from the slope. This new value of n is checked with the earlier obtained one and the same iterative procedure can be repeated until convergence of m and n values to within 1% deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The neat epoxy resin and its blends with 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 phr (based on 100 parts of the epoxy resin), respectively, of PEI were cured at three isothermal temperatures, 177, 187, and 197 °C, and kinetic analysis was performed using the above kinetic models. For space concerns, selected data are presented here. Only the rate curves for the neat epoxy resin and its three blends with 10, 30, and 50 phr of PEI were plotted. The results are shown in Figure 1 (Diagrams 1-A and 1-B for the rate curves obtained at only two of the three isothermal temperatures, 177, and 187 °C, respectively).

Fig. 1. Plot of the reaction rate versus time for neat epoxy and 10, 30, 50 phr PEI/epoxy blends at three different temperatures: (1-A) 177 °C, (1-B) 187 °C.

These rate curves are distinctly autocatalytic in nature, and the maximum rate is seen to occur at 18, 15, and 10 min. of time after start of reaction, respectively, for isothermal reaction temperatures of 177 and 187 °C. The results in the figures also demonstrate that the presence of PEI in the epoxy resin does not effect a change in the autocatalytic nature. However, the reaction rate of the epoxy is clearly enhanced by the presence of polyetherimide since the maximum rate increases with the PEI content in the epoxy blends. The same effect on the epoxy reaction rate was also observed for all the three temperatures studied. The decrease of ΔH with PEI increase should not be taken as a result of PEI weight in the blend. Rather, this was an indication that the reaction mechanism was likely changed by the presence of PEI in the blends. Similar decrease in ΔH was also observed in neat epoxy resins cured with higher concentrations of the amine curing agent.

These data for the epoxy and its blends with PEI were analyzed using the proposed autocatalytic mechanism. The kinetic parameters were determined using the earlier explained procedures. Since there are two kinetic constants, k_1 and k_2 , two activation energies, ΔE_1 and ΔE_2 , could be obtained by plotting $\ln k_1$ and $\ln k_2$, respectively, versus $1/T$. Figure 2 shows the plots of $\ln k_1$ or $\ln k_2$ vs. $1/T$, from which the activation energies were determined for the epoxy and its blends. The reaction orders, m and n , are approximately 0.5 and 1.4, respectively, and the orders do not seem to vary much for the epoxy or the blends of different PEI contents. The values of ΔE_1 and ΔE_2 obtained in this study for the neat amine-cured TGDDM epoxy were 80.2 and 60.9 KJ/mol, respectively, which agreed well with those reported in the literature [22].

Fig. 2 Plot of $\ln k_1$ and $\ln k_2$ against $1/T$ for neat resin and 10, 20, 30, 50 phr PEI/epoxy blends in an autocatalysed reaction.

Figures 3 (Diagrams 3-A and 3-B) shows that the empirical conversion curves fit the experimental data quite well until the cure reactions progress to the vitrification point.

Fig.3. Comparison between the autocatalytic model and data for neat epoxy and 10, 30, 50 phr PEI/epoxy blends at three temperatures: (3-A) 177 °C, (3-B) 187 °C.

Apparently, the model describes the kinetics well but diffusion control in the vitrified state limits the epoxy reactions from going any further. Vitrification is a state where the T_g of the reacting system exceeds the temperature of the system. The T_g of the epoxy phase of the blends was measured by DSC immediately after the completion of isothermal cure. The T_g 's of the cured epoxy blends were found to be 10-15 °C above the cure temperatures, 177 and 187 °C, respectively. After vitrification the progress in the cure reaction almost comes to a stop, therefore the extent of cure is limited. This indicates that the cure kinetics in the later stage was indeed subjected to diffusion control due to vitrification.

CONCLUSION

An autocatalytic mechanism was observed for the amine-cured epoxy-polyetherimide blends of a range of compositions. To probe the mechanism of the observed difference in the cure kinetics between the epoxy-PEI blends and the neat epoxy, the morphology development of the blends as the cure progressed from initial to final stages was examined using SEM. For the epoxy-PEI blends, as the cure progressed, the phase domains went through a series of change. At low cure extents, partial miscibility existed between the epoxy and PEI phases, and the domain boundary was less obvious. As the cure progressed, segregation of the phases became more apparent, and the domains changed in relative sizes. As a result, the amine curing agent (DDS) was

unevenly distributed, and local segregation of DDS in the epoxy-rich domain owing to phase separation resulted in a slightly higher concentration of DDS.

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